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Fuzzy modeling supply chain business processes

The subject of the study is a set of theoretical, scientific and practical provisions regarding the assessment of the effectiveness of business process management in supply chains.

The purpose of the study is to develop a model for evaluating the management of business processes in supply chains using the method of fuzzy logic.

Research methods. In order to comply with the conceptual integrity of scientific development, the dialectical method of scientific cognition, as well as empirical–theoretical and formal–logical principles were used.

Results of work. Economic and mathematical modeling of business process management in supply chains was performed on the basis of fuzzy logic. The developed model allows you to determine the level of effectiveness of the business process management system, reveals its shortcomings, and allows you to monitor the dynamics of general indicators.

Field of application of results. The presented developments can be used in evaluating the effectiveness of business process management in supply chains.

Conclusions. The use of the developed model based on the fuzzy logic approach will contribute to obtaining substantiated data on the state of performance of business processes and relevant recommendations on the formation of their management strategies.

Key words: management, business process, supply chains, fuzzy logic.

КЛИМЧУК МАРИНА
СВИСТУН ВІЛЬЯМ
ШОВКІВСЬКА ВІКТОРІЯ

Нечітке моделювання бізнес–процесів ланцюга поставок

Предметом дослідження є сукупність теоретичних, науково–практичних положень щодо оцінювання результативності управління бізнес–процесами в ланцюгах поставок.

Метою дослідження є розробка моделі оцінювання управління бізнес–процесами в ланцюгах поставки з використанням методу нечіткої логіки.

Методи дослідження. З метою дотримання концептуальної цілісності наукової розробки використано діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, а також емпірико–теоретичний та формально–логічний принципи.

Результати роботи. На основі підходу нечітких множин виконано економіко–математичне моделювання управління бізнес–процесами в ланцюгах поставки, розроблена модель дозволяє визначати рівень результативності системи управління бізнес–процесами, розкриває її недоліки, дозволяє прослідкувати динаміку узагальнюючих показників.

Галузь застосування результатів. Представлені розробки можна використовувати при оцінюванні результативності управління бізнес–процесами ланцюгах поставки.

Висновки. Використання розробленої моделі на основі нечітко–множинного підходу сприятиме отриманню обґрунтованих даних про стан результативності бізнес–процесів та відповідних рекомендацій щодо формування стратегій управління ними.

Ключові слова: управління, бізнес–процес, ланцюги поставки, fuzzy logic.

Introduction. Business process management can help enterprises view their supply chains comprehensively and optimize them for better performance. BPM

can provide those benefits not just throughout an individual enterprise, but to outside suppliers, partners and other key parties as well. Ultimately, BPM can im-

prove efficiency, visibility, control, and accountability throughout the entire supply chain [2].

The formation of a system for managing business processes in supply chains requires providing relationship between management decisions that have been made and the results obtained as a result of their implementation. The means of establishing such a relationship is evaluation, the essence of which is to determine the value of the obtained results.

Business processes management in supply chains, such results consist of many effects (for example, an increase in sales volume, number of customers, profit, profitability, creation of a positive image of the company, increase in customer satisfaction as a result of transactions).

Such a diversity of the results of the implementation of business processes in supply chains complicates the task of their evaluation. Therefore, scientific studies devoted to the development of economic and mathematical models based on fuzzy logic are relevant.

Literature review. Tom Dwyer said that in today's demanding business environment, that prioritizes flexibility, speed, quality, efficiency, effectiveness and innovation, a competitive supply chain strategy and its operational execution is critical. Business Process Management (BPM) helps an enterprise achieve these characteristics in its supply chain strategy – and in its execution of that strategy. Applying the BPM discipline achieves process improvements that lead to organizational performance improvements – such as a Supply Chain [8].

Sustainable supply chain management still faces several academic and practical challenges in terms of implementation, performance measurement, and how models can capture a dynamic and uncertain social and environmental context. There are latent research issues such as management of the circular supply chain, applications in emerging economies, or the application of 4.0 technologies [1].

Fuzzy logic is a technique suitable for dealing with uncertainty and subjectivity, which becomes an interesting auxiliary approach to manage performance of supply chains [2].

Lori Kinney highlights the following benefits at each level of business process management in supply chains: spend less resources, reduce more risk, maintain contingency plans management [3].

The purpose of the study is to develop a model for evaluating the management of business processes in supply chains using the method of fuzzy logic.

Methodology. The dynamic economic environment complicates the process of assessing the effectiveness of business process management in supply chains, which determines the use of economic and mathematical modeling, which takes into account the uncertainties of modern conditions for the implementation of supply chains.

For an organization to operate efficiently and effectively, it's important that there is a clear understanding of how work is done. In an increasingly interconnected world, the delivery of products and services relies on collaboration with multiple external partners and suppliers. Ensuring that the right information and parts get to the right place at the right time is crucial and supply chain process management can be a key enabler for this. It is worth starting with a definition of supply chain management. The following definition from Daniel Stanton is particularly useful: «Supply chain management is the planning and coordination of all of the people, processes, and technology involved in creating value for a company. [...] In other words, it means looking at your business as a single link in a long, end-to-end chain that supplies something of value to a customer» [11].

The analysis of existing methods in the management of business processes in supply chains leads to conclusions about the need to develop an approach to modeling using the apparatus of fuzzy logic, which provides the opportunity to form a model taking into account the quantitative and qualitative indicators of a specific business entity. The use of a fuzzy approach makes it possible to solve important tasks of business process management in supply chains, in particular, comprehensive consideration of uncertainty factors associated with the peculiarities of the functioning of enterprises in modern conditions.

The extreme abstractness of mathematical models, which are built using the apparatus of fuzzy logic and neural networks, is an indisputable advantage, as it makes them suitable for describing almost any system, regardless of the nature of the latter, which is a sufficient prerequisite for making forecasts and developing business management strategies – processes in supply chains.

In our research [6–7], we proposed that the system of indicators for assessing the effectiveness of business process management includes indicators of business process management in these subsystems, where the first level is represented by business management processes that perform administrative and management functions and make management

decisions. The second level is represented by the main business processes of the organization or the production subsystem. The third level is the supporting business processes – the financial and economic subsystem. At the fourth level are the business processes of development, or the innovation subsystem.

Analysis of the business process management system in supply chains using the fuzzy logic apparatus, first of all, it is necessary to form a set of individual indicators that are the most important for evaluation. The supply chain business process management system (Y) can be evaluated based on the values of generalized groups of indicators:

$$Y = fY (X1, X2, X3, X4) \quad (1)$$

X_i – is the corresponding i -th group of indicators.

As a result of the selection of indicators, a model, which is a neural fuzzy network, was obtained. Thus, a neural network is a multilayer perceptron with one inner layer, and its input, intermediate and output parameters, regardless of their nature, are considered as linguistic variables defined on their universal sets and evaluated using fuzzy terms [9].

$$X \in X_1, \dots, X_N, i = 1, N, j = 1, M$$

N – number of generalized groups ($N=4$);

M – the number of indicators in the group.

Each indicator is compared with its level of significance for the analysis.

The level of significance is indicated r_i . To assess this level, all indicators are arranged in order of decreasing importance in such a way that the rule is followed:

$$r_1 \geq r_2 \geq \dots r_N \quad (2)$$

After that, the significance of the i th indicator is determined according to the Fishburn rule [109], namely:

$$r_i = 2(N-i+1)/(N+1)N \quad (3)$$

If the indicators have the same significance, then

$$r_i = 1/N \quad (4)$$

In order to qualitatively assess all levels of economic parameters, we will define the linguistic variable «Indicator level», the set of values of which will be represented by the following subsets (terms): K_r – «critical» level; D_N – «very low» level; H – «low» level; D – «sufficient» level; B is a «high» level, i.e. five levels of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains are offered.

The membership function «Efficiency level of business process management» was specified using a standard five-level classifier [10] (the range [0,1] is divided into five equal intervals, each of which is represented as a fuzzy number with its own membership function).

A «critical» level of business process management efficiency in supply chains means that there is full confidence that the efficiency of functional subsystems is low. It is possible that the level of efficiency in a separate functional subsystem is average, but the low value of indicators for other subsystems reduces the integral characteristic of the effectiveness of business process management in supply chains. The goals set by the company were not achieved.

The level of efficiency of business process management in supply chains is «very low», which means that it is quite possible that management in individual functional subsystems (one or two) is characterized by an average level. However, the low performance of the rest of the subsystems reduces the integral characteristic of business process management. Growth dynamics are observed, but its pace is slowed down.

The level of management of business processes in supply chains is «low» means that there is full confidence that the effectiveness of the work performed within the functional subsystems of the enterprise is of an average level. It is possible that average performance is supported by above-average/high performance in some (one or two) subsystems. The company achieved its goals, but the costs of achieving them exceeded the planned level. The growth dynamics corresponds to its pace.

The level of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains is «sufficient» means that the company effectively performs its functions, but some subsystems (one or two) have a low level of management effectiveness. The set goals have been achieved, but the low level of management efficiency of individual functional subsystems should cause an adequate response from management. Growth rates are ahead of growth dynamics.

The characteristic «Effectiveness level of business process management in supply chains», how high it means effective execution of business processes and achievement of set goals. Stable dynamics of growth rates are observed.

To describe the membership function, a trapezoidal function was chosen.

It is presented in Figure 3, it is called a fuzzy number.

Associated with the normal number axis (horizontal axis) is the confidence axis of the number value (vertical axis, density value of the fuzzy measure), and each value on the horizontal axis (carrier) is given some confidence value (from 0 to 1).

Characterization of levels of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains

Analytical expression of management performance levels business processes in supply chains based on fuzzy logic	Characterization of levels of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains	The economic essence of levels of management effectiveness business processes in supply chains
$Z1(Y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 0 \leq Y < 0.15 \\ [10 \cdot (0.25 - Y)] & \text{if } 0.15 \leq Y < 0.25 \\ 0 & \text{if } 0.25 \leq Y \leq 1 \end{cases}$	«Critical» level of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains	There are no growth dynamics
$Z2(Y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0 \leq Y < 0.15 \\ [10 \cdot (Y - 0.15)] & \text{if } 0.15 \leq Y < 0.25 \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.25 \leq Y < 0.35 \\ [10 \cdot (0.45 - Y)] & \text{if } 0.35 \leq Y < 0.45 \\ 0 & \text{if } 0.45 \leq Y \leq 1 \end{cases}$	The level of effectiveness of business process management is «very low»	The dynamics of growth are observed, but the pace of growth has slowed down
$Z3(Y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0 \leq Y < 0.35 \\ [10 \cdot (Y - 0.35)] & \text{if } 0.35 \leq Y < 0.45 \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.45 \leq Y < 0.55 \\ [10 \cdot (0.65 - Y)] & \text{if } 0.55 \leq Y < 0.65 \\ 0 & \text{if } 0.65 \leq Y \leq 1 \end{cases}$	«Low» level of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains	Growth dynamics correspond to growth rates
$Z4(Y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0 \leq Y < 0.55 \\ [10 \cdot (Y - 0.55)] & \text{if } 0.55 \leq Y < 0.65 \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.65 \leq Y < 0.75 \\ [10 \cdot (0.85 - Y)] & \text{if } 0.75 \leq Y < 0.85 \\ 0 & \text{if } 0.85 \leq Y \leq 1 \end{cases}$	The level of effectiveness of business process management in supply chains is «adequate»	Growth rates are ahead of growth dynamics
$Z5(Y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0 \leq Y < 0.75 \\ [10 \cdot (Y - 0.75)] & \text{if } 0.75 \leq Y < 0.85 \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.85 \leq Y \leq 1 \end{cases}$	«High» level of performance of business process management in supply chains	There is a stable growth rate dynamics

Trapezoidal view of the performance indicator of business process management in supply chains

As a result, the figure represents the dependence of the confidence that a given variable (numerical value) will take one or the other. The main difference between numerical quantities

described by fuzzy numbers is that the quantity is blurred on a numerical interval. The reasons for this blurring are factors of uncertainty. These factors lead to the fact that the value of

the quantity may be to the left or to the right of the most expected clear number.

The presence of unclear descriptions in the structure of the model is related to the uncertainty of the expert, which arises during the classification of the level of factors.

The upper base of the trapezoid will correspond to the expert's full confidence in the classification of the factor, and the lower one – none of the values in the interval $(0,1)$ fall into the selected fuzzy set [4–5].

After evaluating the ranges of the values of the membership functions for each of the indicators, we calculate their values, that is, the ranks – the values of the membership functions of the indicators to the unclear levels of the variable «Level of the indicator». At the same time, all indicators will have a vague representation of the form:

$$\beta(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4), \quad (5)$$

a_1, a_4 – respectively, abscissas of the lower base of the trapezoid of the corresponding level; a_2, a_3 – respectively, the abscissas of the upper base of the trapezoid of the corresponding level.

That is, if the value of the indicator lies between the abscissas of the upper edge of the trapezoid ($a_2 \leq X_n \leq a_3$), the value of λ will be equal to 1, otherwise the values of the membership function λ are calculated by the formula of the ordinate of the side edge of the trapezoid for both subsets of the verbal (linguistic) variable «Indicator level». Let us give the analytical form of recording the trapezoidal membership function of the fuzzy term B of the input variable X1.

$$\mu^B(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < a_1 \\ a_2 - x/a_2 - a_1, & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ 1, & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ a_4 - x/a_4 - a_3, & a_3 \leq x \leq a_4 \\ 0, & x > a_4 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$\mu(x)$ – the function of belonging of the original variable X to the fuzzy term li, li {Kp; ДН; Н; Д; В}.

The integral assessment of the business process management system in supply chains is calculated according to the following formula:

– integral index of a subgroup of indices; the weight of each group of indicators.

Conclusion

Based on the approach of fuzzy sets, economic and mathematical modeling of business process management in supply chains was performed, the developed model allows to determine the level of

effectiveness of the business process management system, reveals its shortcomings, and allows to follow the dynamics of generalizing indicators. The proposed model based on the use of fuzzy logic, characterized by flexibility and adaptability to changing market conditions, allows you to determine the level of efficiency of the business process management system in supply chains, reveals its shortcomings, and allows you to study the dynamics of generalizing indicators of each functional subsystem. The evaluation proposals provided will contribute to obtaining sound data on important business processes in supply chains and appropriate recommendations for the formation of strategies for their management.

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КРАМЧЕНКО Р. А.
ПИЛИПІВ І. Р.

Пріоритети та проблеми розвитку машинобудівних підприємств на сучасному етапі

Предметом дослідження є пріоритети та проблеми розвитку машинобудівних підприємств на сучасному етапі.

Метою дослідження є визначити шляхи подолання системної кризи машинобудівних підприємств.

Методи дослідження. У роботі використані діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, метод аналізу і синтезу, порівняльний метод, метод узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті окреслені основні проблеми негативної динаміки підприємств. Наведена схема реструктуризації великих підприємств. Встановлено основні причини, які стримують виробництво та збут продукції. Визначено ряд стратегічних та тактичних завдань функціонування спільних підприємств.

Висновки. Диспропорція у економічній та фінансовій галузях, відсутність контрактів і замовлень, забезпечених надійним фінансуванням продовжує системну кризу галузі сільськогосподарського машинобудування України. Нестача сільськогосподарської техніки в агропромисловому секторі, потенційні можливості виробників, активна збутова маркетингова діяльність разом з прийнятою державною програмою з насичення вітчизняного ринку конкурентоспроможною сільськогосподарською технікою створюють об'єктивні передумови для збільшення обсягів її виробництва та збуту. Разом із тим, серед гальмуючих чинників зростання обсягів виробництва та збуту залишаються: наявність застарілого обладнання, велика конкуренція на ринках збуту, низька платоспроможність попиту споживачів, недостатність залучення інвестицій.

Ключові слова: підприємство, ринок, збут, маркетинг, конкурентоспроможність, інвестиції, інформація, інновації, фінанси, споживачі.